

CRU CY 3.21 - Data availability and File Formats explained

Where to find the CRU CY 3.21 data files:

The CRU CY 3.21 data are available from the BADC Archive at:

http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/browse/badc/cru/data/cru_cy/cru_cy_3.21

Please, note that the 'DJF' (winter) value for the last year will be missing (-999.0 value); this is because the season straddles two years, and cannot be calculated without the January and February values.

CRU CY 3.21 Data File Format explained:

Each country file contains all the spatial means for a particular country and variable. The files are ASCII text, and should be readable with almost any application including a text editor (they import into Excel readily, start the import at line 4 or 5).

Each file begins with three information lines:

- Line 1: Includes the date and time of production, and the date string uniquely identifying the CRU TS run on which the dataset is based.
- Line 2: Identifies the country, parameter (variable) and units (eg, mm).
- Line 3: Contains the time period, the missing value code, and the data format (as a Fortran-style string).

There is then a data header, describing the following columns:

YEAR
JAN-DEC (12 columns, monthly means)
MAM, JJA, SON, DJF (4 columns, seasonal means)
ANN (annual mean)

After these lines come the data, one line per year.

- Units:

Label	Variable	Units	Comments
cld	Cloud Cover	percentage	
dtr	Diurnal Temperature Range	Degrees Celcius	the diurnal temperature range is the difference between the daily minimum and maximum temperatures
frs	Frost Day Frequency	Days	Frost days are constructed synthetically from monthly TMN. The process is described in: Representing Twentieth-Century Space-Time Climate Variability. Part II: Development of 1901-96 Monthly Grids of Terrestrial Surface Climate; New et al (2000). A frost day is a period of 24 hours in which the minimum temperature falls below 0°C. If the temperature stays below zero all day, that's an 'ice day'.
pet	Potential Evapo-Transpiration (PET)	Millimetres	The method used is the FAO (Food and Agricultural Organization) grass reference evapotranspiration equation (Ekstrom et al., 2007, which is based on Allen et al., 1994). It is a variant of the Penman Monteith method using the gridded TMP, TMN, TMX, VAP and CLD. Note that PET values are mean mm/day for each month. The pet values in the datafiles therefore need to be multiplied by the number of days for each month to get the mean pet for that month.
pre	Precipitation	Millimetres	
tmp	Daily mean temperature	Degrees Celcius	The daily 'mean' temperature is the mid-point (median) between the daily minimum and maximum temperatures.
tmn	Monthly average daily minimum temperature	Degrees Celcius	
tmx	Monthly average daily maximum temperature	Degrees Celcius	
vap	Vapour pressure	Hecta-Pascals	
wet	Wet Day Frequency (rain days per month)	Days	

CRU CY 3.21 Data Processing in brief:

The CRU CY dataset is an update of the [TYN CY dataset](#), which may be found on the CRU website. Please note that unlike the previous TYN CY dataset, CRU CY consists solely of country averages.

The original data (CRU TS 3.21) took the form of a value for each month and each box on a 0.5 degree latitude/longitude grid. CRU assigned each box to a single country. For each country CRU calculated the weighted mean of the values from its constituent grid boxes for each month in turn. Each grid box was weighted by surface area, using the cosine of the latitude. The seasonal and annual values are the means of their constituent months. The CRU TS dataset prioritises completeness, and has no missing data over land. Where observations are unavailable, the 1961-90 monthly climatic mean is used as a substitute. In data sparse regions of the world, this can lead to repeated values, and this can show up in derived products such as CRU CY.

Advisory Note issued on 29th August 2013:

An advisory note was issued by CRU in the summer 2013 concerning a spatial area of Northeast Africa, for the PRE and WET variables only of CRU CY3.21. An error has been detected in new Mozambique precipitation observations introduced in 2011 for the CRU TS v3.20 dataset and continuing to be used in the CRU TS v3.21 dataset. The new stations had the signs of their latitudes swapped, so that they appeared north of the equator instead of south of it. Thus, the erroneous station data affects cells in an area corresponding to Mozambique if it were 'mirrored' in the equator.

The error impacts on both PRE and WET data (as WET is derived from PRE).

An examination of the error found 35 new stations that had been incorrectly located. A test run using corrected data was used to construct annual averages for each country, allowing comparison with the published data (v3.21). [Comparison plots \(pdfs\)](#) are available in the CRU-CY3.21 archive.

A visual inspection identifies Eritrea and Egypt as those countries showing the greatest changes, though some others show small differences in one or two years.

Disclaimer:

The author bears no responsibility for the accuracy of the data set. The countries listed below include a variety of sovereign states, dependent territories, and disputed territories. No political statement is being made by the inclusion or exclusion of a particular territory, or by the labelling of a particular territory by a particular name.